

EFFECT OF FRICTION BETWEEN UHMWPE AND PMMA ON THE SHOULDER ARTHROPLASTY

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SUMMARY: The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of friction between PMMA bone cement and UHMWPE glenoid component on stresses and tilting using a FE model. The FE model of a cemented glenoid component was loaded with a joint compression and subluxation force of 725 and 350 N, respectively, with different coefficients of friction in the PMMA/UHMWPE interface. The maximal principal stresses in the cement layer ranged between 21.30 and 32.18 MPa. Glenoid component tilting ranged between 0.943° and 0.513°. It was found that the interface condition has a large effect on the maximal principal stresses and glenoid component tilting. Whether adhesion between the UHMWPE component and PMMA bone cement occurs, is unknown beforehand and, as a result, design validation using the FE technique should be done both by using contact elements in combination with a coefficient of friction as well as a full bonding at this interface.

KEYWORDS: prosthesis design, FEM, UHMWPE, PMMA, interface, cement stresses, glenoid component tilting.

INTRODUCTION

Total shoulder arthroplasty is a common treatment for patients suffering from rheumatoid-arthritis and osteoarthritis, as well as in the case of humerus fractures. A conventional total shoulder arthroplasty consists of a metallic convex humerus component articulating against a concave Ultra-High-Molecular-Weight-Poly-Ethylene (UHMWPE) glenoid component [1].

The main objective of this treatment is pain relief, which is achieved in most cases. However, results in terms of survival rates and post-operative shoulder functionality must be improved to increase long-term patient satisfaction [2,3]. These results are influenced by patient characteristics, design of the prosthesis and surgical factors [4]. One of the methods to improve the results of shoulder replacements is to develop improved prosthesis designs. New designs must be validated, which can be done by experimental testing, including quasi-static and fatigue tests, and numerical tools, e.g. the Finite Element (FE) method.

The FE method is very useful for investigating the performance of prosthesis designs, as this method allows for good parameter control, is fast and relatively cheap. However, the complex FE models of artificial joints consist of many important details, which are not unambiguous and need discussion. One of these details for discussion is the cement-prosthesis interface, in the case of UHMWPE components cemented by Polymethyl-Methacrylate (PMMA). This interface may be physically unbonded, not only years after in-vivo use, but also direct post-operatively, as demonstrated by in-house experiments and from literature [5,6]. Many FE models assume this interface to be rigidly bonded, which might not always be correct, as also discussed by Stone et al. (1999) [7] and Couteau et al. (2001) [8].

According to the authors, the effect of the conditions of this interface on the strains and stresses in orthopedic components and the underlying cement layer and bone is still unknown. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of the interface condition between PMMA bone cement and the UHMWPE component on cement stresses and glenoid component tilting, a measure for upward and downward glenoid component rotation due to glenoid rim-displacements, in a FE model. To investigate this effect, the coefficient of friction (cof) between PMMA and UHMWPE was also investigated as no values are found in literature. Subsequently, the experimental measurements of the coefficient of friction between UHMWPE en PMMA and the FE study to the effect of the interface condition between PMMA bone cement and the UHMWPE component on cement stresses and glenoid component tilting will be presented and finally a general conclusion will be given.

NOTATION

- c_g Glenoid chord length from superior to inferior (mm)
 cof Coefficient of friction
 d_i Displacement of the inferior glenoid rim in the medial-lateral direction (mm)
 d_s Displacement of the superior glenoid rim in the medial-lateral direction (mm)
 D, D_c PMMA specimen diameter fitting in the PMMA specimen holder and contacting the UHMWPE sheet material, respectively (mm)
 F_c Joint contact force, perpendicular to the articular surfaces ($\overline{F_s} + \overline{F_z}$) (N)
 F_s Applied subluxation force, acting at the center of the humeral head, (N)
 F_z Compression force acting at the center of the humeral head in the z -direction (N)
 h PMMA specimen height (mm)
 R_g, R_h Radius of curvature of the glenoid and humeral component, respectively (mm)
 y, z Directions in the co-ordinate system
 λ Glenoid tilting, rotation due to glenoid rim-displacements, $\lambda = \sin^{-1}((d_s - d_i)/c_g)$ ($^\circ$)

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the artificial shoulder joint (a) and of the loaded glenoid structure, which is the basis of the FE study, also demonstrating glenoid component tilting λ , due to glenoid rim-displacements d_s and d_i (see the notation)

THE COEFFICIENT OF FRICTION BETWEEN UHMWPE AND PMMA

Methods and materials of the cof measurements

The dynamic coefficient of friction (cof), in a dry and wet (water) environment for different contact pressures has been measured in a preliminary study, described elsewhere [9], of which the results are also given in Table 2.

In the present study, the static cof between UHMWPE and PMMA in a wet and dry environment for different contact pressures, were measured. Cylindrical PMMA specimens (Palamed G20, Biomet Merck, Dordrecht, The Netherlands) were used contacting UHMWPE sheet material (Chirulen 1020, Poly-Hi Solidur GmbH, Vreden, Germany) (for material

properties see Table 1). The PMMA specimens were made by turning and have a height h of 6 mm, divided in a part with a specimen diameter D of 6.51 mm fitting in the PMMA specimen holder and a part with diameter D_c of 6.51, 4.61, 3.76, 3.26 or 2.91 mm (Figure 2), contacting the counteracting UHMWPE sheet material.

During measurements of the dynamic cof [9], the surface of the relatively brittle and more porous PMMA specimens becomes filled with the softer UHMWPE, resulting in a smoother PMMA specimen surface. This is demonstrated using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) photo's (Scanning Microscope Jeol, JSM840A, Japan). As can be seen in Figure 2, there is a clear qualitative difference in the surface porosity between new PMMA specimens and specimens used for measuring the dynamic cof. As the PMMA bone cement may also be filled by UHMWPE in-vivo, the static cof was also measured of these already used PMMA specimens. Before testing, all PMMA specimens were abraded against 1000 FEPA P-grade sandpaper, except for the UHMWPE filled PMMA specimens. This was done to make sure that all three PMMA specimens had full surface contact with the UHMWPE disc and that all PMMA specimens had equal surface roughness.

In combination with a static load of 100 N, applied by weights and distributed over three identical PMMA specimens, this leads to contact pressures ranging between 1.0 and 5.0 Mpa, which is of the same order as the maximal principal cements stresses found in literature [7].

Just before testing, specimens were cleaned using isopropanol. The dry and wet (water) coefficient of friction were measured at environmental conditions at room temperature. A force sensor was connected to the triangular specimen holder, which measures the manually applied, increasing pulling force (see Figure 3). The force sensor was connected to a signal amplifier (Peekel Instruments B.V., Rotterdam, The Netherlands), which recorded the maximal applied force. This maximal applied force occurs just before the triangular specimen holder starts to move and is a measure for the static cof. This experiment was repeated three times with different specimens for each contact pressure.

In this study, the static cof in a wet and dry environment of both new and UHMWPE filled PMMA specimens were measured. In combination with the preliminary study on the dynamic cof [9], this led to six different coefficients of friction with contact pressures ranging between 1 and 5 MPa. To investigate the significance of the obtained differences of the six different test conditions, the results were averaged with respect to the contact pressure and compared using the unpaired t-test with a confidential level of 95%.

Fig. 2: Specimen geometry (a) and Scanning Electron Microscope photo's of the used PMMA specimens (b,c,d). (a) The rotational symmetric PMMA specimens ($h=6$ mm, $D=6$ mm for clamping in the metal holder, $D_c=6.51$, 4.61, 3.76, 3.26 or 2.91 mm contacting the UHMPE sheet material) (b) Complete surface area, partially filled with UHMWPE (12x). (c) Detail of a porous location (150x). (d) Detail of a UHMWPE-filled location (300x)

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the materials used [10]

	Experimental		FEM			
	UHMWP	PMMA	UHMWP	PMMA	CoCr	Bone substitute
Young's Modulus (GPa)	0.80 – 1.50	2.2 – 3.1	1.0	2.733	210	0.1375
Poisson's ratio (-)	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3
Strength (ultimate) (MPa)	27	88	-	-	-	-
Yield strength (MPa)	19	52 - 71	-	-	-	-

Fig: 3 Test set-up for measuring the static coefficient of friction. 1. Metal holder for the UHMWPE sheet specimens. 2. UHMWPE specimens (3x). 3. Peekel signal amplifier. 4. Force transducer 5. PMMA specimen holder. 6. Weight. (b) Assembled test set-up

Results of the measurements of the cof between UHMWPE and PMMA

The results are presented in Table 2 and graphically in Figure 4, to better demonstrate the influence of the contact pressure on the cof. The dynamic cof in a dry and wet environment averaged 0.296 and 0.113, respectively [9], whereas the static cof in a dry and wet environment averaged 0.297 and 0.252, respectively. The obtained differences, averaged for the contact pressure for the dry and wet test conditions, are significant ($p < 0.05$). The differences between the dynamic and static cof for the dry and wet test condition are not-significant ($p > 0.05$) and significant ($p < 0.05$), respectively. The static cof of the UHMWPE-filled specimens in a wet and dry environment averaged 0.153 and 0.142, respectively, which are both significantly different ($p < 0.05$) compared to the static cof of new specimens, for the dry and wet test condition.

Discussion of the measurements of the cof between UHMWPE and PMMA

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of the interface condition between PMMA bone cement and the UHMWPE component on cement stresses and glenoid component tilting in a FE model. To achieve this aim, the cof between PMMA bone cement and UHMWPE has been investigated. The cof for a given material combination may be influenced by many parameters, such as surface roughness and method of manufacturing of the specimens, loading conditions etc. However, this study was not meant to investigate all influencing parameters on the cof, but just to provide a cof for a specific application.

Detailed contact properties of the PMMA - UHMWPE interface for in-vivo conditions are still unknown. As a result, different test-conditions are used to investigate if and to what extent interface conditions have an effect on the cof. As also the fluid properties at the PMMA – UHMWPE interface are unknown, water is used as a lubricant. From literature it is known that a somewhat higher cof can be expected when serum is used instead of water [10].

It is found that a lower cof is found in the case of a wet test condition. The fluid film separates the opposing surfaces and any load is carried by the pressure generated within the lubricant. As there is no direct contact between the surfaces, the cof is lower for wet test conditions. In the case of the dynamic test condition, this is intensified by 'elastohydrodynamic lubrication' (EHL). EHL causes improved fluid film lubrication, which is the result of a velocity difference between the two surfaces, creating a pressure difference at the tops of roughness peaks, thereby deforming these peaks and preventing direct contact [12].

In this study, a non-significant difference was found between the static and dynamic cof in a dry environment. Even a larger dynamic than static cof was found for contact pressures of 2 and 3 Mpa, which is found more often in literature [13]. In the two studies it was practically not possible to use the same equipment and environmental conditions were also different.

Table 2: Dynamic and static coefficient of friction for different test conditions and contact pressures (MPa) ($n=3$, average (SD))

Condition Pressure	Dynamic / Dry	Dynamic / Wet	Static / Dry	Static / Wet	Static / UHMWPE filled / filled / Wet	Static / UHMWPE filled / filled / Wet
1	0.298 (0.018)	0.127 (0.009)	0.299 (0.027)	0.261 (0.024)	0.152 (0.012)	0.138 (0.006)
2	0.305 (0.021)	0.124 (0.014)	0.295 (0.025)	0.247 (0.032)	-	-
3	0.305 (0.031)	0.121 (0.016)	0.285 (0.028)	0.23 (0.015)	0.178 (0.011)	0.168 (0.008)
4	0.294 (0.012)	0.09 (0.002)	0.31 (0.023)	0.241 (0.02)	-	-
5	0.255 (0.048)	0.102 (0.007)	0.296 (0.022)	0.28 (0.026)	0.129 (0.011)	0.121 (0.007)
Average	0.296 (0.038)	0.113 (0.017)	0.297 (0.003)	0.252 (0.006)	0.153 (0.025)	0.142 (0.024)

Fig. 4 Dynamic and static coefficient of friction as function of the contact pressure in a wet and dry test conditions. * PMMA specimens filled with UHMWPE

EFFECT OF THE INTERFACE CONDITION ON THE RESULTS OF FE MODELING OF THE GLENOID STRUCTURE

Methods and materials

Effect of the interface condition has been investigated for maximal principal stresses and medial-lateral displacements of the glenoid component, PMMA bone cement and bone substitute. The superior d_s and inferior d_i glenoid component rim-displacements may result in glenoid component tilting λ , calculated as $\sin^{-1}((d_s-d_i)/c_g)$, where c_g is the glenoid superior-inferior chord length. This tilting may be the underlying cause of glenoid component loosening, especially if it causes tensile stresses in the bone cement layer.

To investigate these effects, a three-dimensional FE model of the artificial glenoid structure has been developed (see Figure 5). The model consists of 42.417 C3D4 tetraeder elements and is analyzed using ABAQUS, version 6.3-3 (ABAQUS Inc., Pawtucket, USA).

Geometry

The geometry of the FE model is based on an experimental test set-up as used in preliminary studies (Figure 1) [12]. Half the original symmetrical test specimen has been modelled, which is a rectangular bone block, representing the glenoid part of the scapula, with outer dimensions of 20x50x40 mm (wxhxd) (see Figure 5). Furthermore, the model consists of a 2 mm cement layer and a commercially available keeled glenoid component with a radius of curvature R_g of 29 mm, radial thickness of 7 mm and height c_g of 38.5 mm. The joint contact force is applied using a humeral indenter with radius of curvature R_h of 24 mm

Material properties

The Young's modulus of 137.5 MPa of the bone structure is chosen according to the previously performed experimental tests [12] and is within the range as found by Frich et al.

Fig: 5 The three-dimensional Finite Element Model. 1. CoCr Humeral head 2. UHMWPE Glenoid component 3. PMMA Cement layer 4. Bone structure 5, 6, 7. Wall constraints. Both the plane of symmetry and the parallel anterior wall are constrained in normal direction. F_s and F_z are the applied joint subluxation and compression forces, respectively

(1997) [14]. Other mechanical properties of the bone as well as of other materials used in the FE model can be found in Table 1. The distribution of the materials in the FE model is shown in Figure 5. All materials are assumed linear elastic.

Interface conditions

At the interface between the humeral indenter and the glenoid component a cof of 0.1 is assumed, whereas between the bone cement and the underlying bone a full bonding has been applied, which is a node-by-node connection of the two surfaces. Between the cement layer and glenoid component the six measured coefficients of friction (see the final row in Table 2) as well as 0, 0.01, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1 have been applied. Additionally, a full bonding has been applied, which represents complete adhesion between UHMWPE and PMMA. As a result, a total of 13 analyses were carried out.

Applied forces and boundary conditions

A joint compression force F_z of 725 N and a joint subluxation force F_s in superior direction of 350 N are applied at the center of the humeral head indenter. These forces correspond to arm abduction up to 90°, as analyzed in a musculoskeletal model [15].

All nodes on the inferior, medial and anterior wall as well as on the plane of symmetry of the bone structure are constrained in both normal directions of these planes. Of the superior wall of the bone structure, only the nodes on the medial half are constrained in both normal directions of this plane (see Figure 5). This is to allow for a more natural deformation pattern, similar to the experimental test set-up [12]. No rotational constraints are applied.

Type of analysis

A geometrically non-linear analysis is carried out in two steps, in which subsequently the compression force and the subluxation force are applied, respectively.

Results of the FE study

An overview of the results of the maximal principal stresses and medial-lateral displacements of the glenoid structure of the 13 analyses can be found in Table 3. Figure 8 gives the maximal principal stresses and the superior d_s and inferior d_i glenoid component rim-displacements, respectively, as a function of the coefficient of friction at the interface as well as in the case of full bonding.

Clear differences were found in maximal principal stresses in the UHMWPE glenoid component, the PMMA bone cement and the bone structure for the different interface conditions. In the glenoid component, the difference of the maximal principal stresses due to different interface conditions, where a full bonding at the interface is taken as the reference (20.74 MPa), ranged between -15.8% (cof=0) and -8.8% (cof=1). In the bone cement, with a

maximal principal stress of 21.3 MPa in the case of full bonding, this difference ranged between +24.5% (cof=0.113, which is the dynamic cof in a wet environment) and +51.1% (cof=0). Finally, the difference of the maximal principal stress in the bone structure ranged between +11.5% (cof=1) and +18.8% (cof=0), relating to an analysis with a full bonding at the interface (29.6 MPa).

Also, clear differences were found in tilting of the glenoid component, the PMMA bone cement and the bone structure for the different interface conditions. The difference in glenoid component tilting due to different interface conditions, where the very small tilting with a full bonding at the interface is taken as the reference (0.763°), ranged between +84.1% (cof=0) and +37.0% (cof=0.4). In the bone cement, with a tilting of 0.741° in the case of full bonding, this difference ranged between +15.8% (cof=0.113, which is the dynamic cof in a wet environment) and +9.9% (cof=0.6). Finally, the difference of the maximal medial displacement in the bone structure ranged between +10.4% (cof=0.8) and +15.4% (cof=0), relating to an analysis with a full bonding at the interface (0.739°).

Good correlation is found between the maximal principal stress and the cof at the UHMWPE and PMMA interface for the glenoid component and bone structure, with a correlation R^2 of 0.9407 and 0.9914, respectively. For the maximal principal stress in the cement layer a worse correlation of 0.6038 with the cof is found. For the superior d_s and inferior d_i glenoid rim-displacements, a close to zero (0.0148) and high correlation (0.8964) are found, respectively. All applied interface conditions lead to negative inferior glenoid rim-displacements d_i , although in the case of full bonding this inferior rim-displacement is almost zero (-0.031 mm).

*Table 3: Max. principal stress and medial displacements in the glenoid structure for different interface conditions. * Static / UHMWPE filled, sup. and inf. indicate superior and inferior, respectively.*

		UHMWPE glenoid				PMMA cement			Bone substitute		
		Max. Prin.	Medial displ.		λ	Max. Prin.	Medial displ.		Max. Prin.	Medial displ.	
			d_s	d_i			sup.	inf.		sup.	inf.
dynamic/dry	0.291	17.61	0.565	-0.327	1.33	27.08	0.545	-0.0164	33.87	0.542	-0.0164
dynamic/wet	0.113	17.63	0.560	-0.357	1.37	26.62	0.560	-0.0164	34.45	0.551	-0.016
static/dry	0.297	17.60	0.565	-0.326	1.33	27.04	0.544	-0.0164	33.85	0.542	-0.0164
static/wet	0.252	17.62	0.564	-0.332	1.33	27.18	0.546	-0.164	33.98	0.544	-0.0164
* / dry	0.153	17.74	0.561	-0.349	1.36	26.85	0.550	-0.0163	34.30	0.548	-0.0163
* / wet	0.142	17.76	0.561	-0.351	1.36	28.75	0.550	-0.0163	34.34	0.549	-0.0164
-	0	17.47	0.568	-0.375	1.40	32.18	0.557	-0.0159	35.1	0.557	-0.0159
-	0.01	17.68	0.564	-0.376	1.40	31.66	0.557	-0.0160	35.08	0.555	-0.0160
-	0.4	17.64	0.568	-0.134	1.05	26.66	0.542	-0.0160	33.6	0.539	-0.0160
-	0.6	17.97	0.568	-0.298	1.29	26.7	0.537	-0.0170	33.25	0.534	-0.0170
-	0.8	18.63	0.565	-0.291	1.27	27.76	0.534	-0.0170	33.07	0.531	-0.0170
-	1	18.92	0.563	-0.286	1.26	28.88	0.532	-0.0178	32.95	0.532	-0.0171
-	Tie	20.74	0.482	-0.0307	0.76	21.30	0.467	-0.0307	29.55	0.467	-0.0296
Max.		20.74	0.568	-0.0307	1.40	32.18	0.560	-0.0159	35.1	0.557	-0.0159
Min.		17.47	0.482	-0.375	0.76	21.30	0.467	-0.0307	29.55	0.467	-0.0296

Discussion of the FE study

This study investigated the effect of the interface condition between the UHMWPE glenoid component and the PMMA cement layer on the results in a FE model. The background of this study is that no bonding was found between many glenoid components as found by in-house experiments. However, bonding of these two surfaces depends on many factors, such as the type of UHMWPE and PMMA bone cement used, the method of sterilization as well as storage conditions. Additionally, surface modification techniques may be applied, which influence adhesion characteristics between UHMWPE and PMMA [11]. As a result, in advance it is unknown if the glenoid component will adhere to the bone cement or not. Maximal principal stresses have been used for parameter investigation, as for the materials

Glenoid component **Bone cement** **Bone substitute** **Sup. rim-displacement d_s** **Inf. rim-displacement d_i**
 Fig. 8: Graphical representation of the effect of interface conditions on the maximal principal stresses in the glenoid structure and the glenoid rim-displacements, d_s and d_i , respectively. R^2 is the second order correlation coefficient and * full bonding at the interface

used in the FE model this may be a better tool than the von Mises stresses, normally used for metals. A maximal principal stress of 20.74 MPa in the UHMWPE was found in the case of a full bonding at the interface, which is close to the 25 MPa, as found by Swieszkowski et al. (2003) [16]. This maximal stress is close to the yield strength of UHMWPE and as a result a similar conclusion can be drawn, that UHMWPE wear may indeed occur in joint replacements, as the UHMWPE yield strength may be exceeded.

The FE model as used in this study has not been validated. However, the aim of this study was not to develop a validated, detailed FE model of the scapula to investigate the effect of interface conditions on the results of FE analyses. Our aim was to investigate the effect of the interface condition between PMMA bone cement and the UHMWPE component on cement stresses and glenoid component tilting in a FE model. However, some remarks can be made, when comparing the results of this study with the results of the experiments, on which the FE model is based on [12]. The superior and inferior rim-displacements of the glenoid component show a similar behaviour compared to the experimental measurements. Both results show glenoid component tilting out of the bone cement, opposite to the side of glenoid component loading. This is demonstrated by the large difference of the inferior rim-displacement between the PMMA bone cement and UHMWPE glenoid component, except in the case of a full bonding, which shows similar rim-displacements (Table 3). In the case of a full bonding at the interface this leads to tensile stresses in the bone cement and in all other cases to a gap between the glenoid component and the bone cement. The absolute values of the rim-displacements as calculated by the FE model are more than 1.5 times larger for the superior rim and almost 10 times larger for the inferior rim, with much smaller values. The values in the case of a full bonding in the FE model are of the same order of magnitude to the results of the experimental measurements, although this interface condition was not found in most glenoid specimens during the experiments [12].

Very few similar studies focused on the investigation of the stresses in and around glenoid components using the FE technique. Couteau et al. (2001) investigated the effect of some surgical parameters on the stresses in the cement layer using a 3D FE model of the scapula [8]. Although they validated their FE model by experimental measurements and good agreement was found, nothing was mentioned about the interface conditions between glenoid component and cement. However, some of their results show stresses in the cement layer, which are of the same order of magnitude as found in our study.

The superior d_s and inferior d_i rim-displacements show high and zero correlation with the cof, respectively (see Figure 9). Therefore, it seems that compression of the superior glenoid structure is not influenced by the cof, whereas the effect on deformation of the inferior glenoid structure is clearly present. It is possible that the increasing shear stiffness at the

interface, due to the increased cof, restrains gap formation between the inferior glenoid component and the cement layer.

Whether or not bonding between the glenoid component and the PMMA bone cement is beneficial for component fixation in the case of presently used glenoid component designs is unknown. In the present study, increased maximal principal stresses but less tilting were found in the glenoid component, when applying a full bonding at this interface, compared to contact elements in combination with a cof at this interface. In the cement layer and bone substitute both lower maximal principal stresses and less medial-lateral displacements were found in the case of a full bonding at this interface. With respect to this, it can be concluded that physical adhesion between the UHMWPE glenoid component and the PMMA bone cement can be beneficial for the fixation of glenoid components. Although the presented FE model is different from the FE models with the geometry of a scapula, in which the glenoid components are inserted, the obtained differences of the results still demonstrate the importance of the interface conditions. Although the cof between PMMA and UHMWPE has not been investigated in great detail, just applying one of the measured coefficients of friction in combination with contact elements results in large differences compared to using a full bonding.

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of the interface condition between PMMA bone cement and the UHMWPE component on cement stresses and glenoid component tilting in a FE model. To achieve this aim, the cof between PMMA bone cement and UHMWPE also has been investigated.

It is found that the interface condition has a large effect on the maximal principal stresses and glenoid component tilting. As adhesion between the UHMWPE component and PMMA bone cement is unknown beforehand, design validation using the FE technique should be done by modeling this interface by both contact elements in combination with a cof as well as by using a full bonding.

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